

Deliverable report

**D-2.10. FoodChain-Lab
web application:
Description and
documentation of
software, development of
tutorials and training
material**

JRP6 - NOVA - FBZ1 - 1st Call

Responsible Partner: BfR

Contributing partners: NVI, NIPH

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<p>Dissemination</p> <p><i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i></p>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p><u>Other recipient(s):</u></p>
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NOVA-WP2-TASK5: TRACE-BACK AND RISK MAPPING, THE FOODCHAIN-LAB WEB APPLICATION

1. Introduction

Identifying a specific product causing a foodborne disease outbreak can be difficult, especially when dealing with large amounts of suspicious food items and weak epidemiological evidence. The FoodChain-Lab web application (FCL Web) is an intuitive and user-friendly app that can support public health institutes during foodborne outbreak investigations. It analyses suspicious food items by back- and forward-tracing the supply chain. We developed a model for a faster recognition of products potentially involved in foodborne outbreaks and made it publicly available for the wide audience, by integrating it into the FCL Web ecosystem.

2. Model

The developed model is a derivative from Norström *et al* (<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0134344>). The model takes human case data and sales/distribution data as input. Local data containing spatial information on Norway is loaded during the execution of the script. The model calculates the likelihood of products to be the source of a foodborne-related outbreak. It is meant to allow investigators to save precious time and resources during outbreaks, since it helps to prioritise food items that should be sampled for laboratory analysis. Developments of the model include automatic spatial weighting according to distance from the residual municipality and the population density in the nearest municipalities, faster runtimes, facilitated sensitivity analysis to statistical and epidemiological parameters, improved consumption date estimation and spatial visualization and data quality checking tools.

3. Features of the implementation

In order to simplify the usage of the model we designed an intuitive web application. Several features help the user to execute the model and deliver additional information to grade the model results.

3.1. Guide to execute the model

The NOVA web application provides a step-by-step guide on how to format, input and process all relevant data that is needed to execute the model. While a 'stepper' on the left side of the screen shows the steps until the execution of the model and the possibility for data input, the right side of the screen provides additional information on the data format, model parameters and optional features to adjust and grade the model results. The web app takes JSON and CSV files as input files and indicates if the file is formatted correctly.

Figure 1: User interface of the implementation showing the guide feature

3.2 Availability for the whole EU

The original model was only available for Norway. We improved the model by making it available for the member states of the European Union, the United Kingdom, Norway and Switzerland by using open geospatial data from the EUROSTAT database. The user can decide which country he wants to investigate on the landing page of the web application. After choosing the country and clicking on the button “Start” the data for the chosen country will be loaded.

Figure 2: Landing page of the NOVA web app

3.2. Exclude data from the calculation

In order to adjust the model results the user has the opportunity to filter the input data and remove items from the calculation. This can reduce the runtime of the calculation and the complexity of the results. A special case is the filter for the “product” input. In order to reduce unnecessary options, all products are grouped automatically. The user can now remove certain products from the calculation, instead of certain deliveries of a product.

Figure 3: NOVA implementation showcasing the case file input with the filter feature

3.3. Dynamic map with geospatial information

A map of the chosen country can be investigated during the adjustment of the app. It shows the population density of each municipality of the chosen country. After loading the “cases” data set, it also shows the municipalities an outbreak has occurred in. Both datasets can be hidden for a better overview.

Figure 4: Map feature showing population density (low to high: yellow to red) and amount of cases (low to high: light to dark green)

3.4. Exporting results

The results of the models are shown in a table, sorted by the likelihood a product is the vehicle of infection in a foodborne disease outbreak. In case a further investigation of this output is needed the results and additional information of the results can be saved on the local machine in a JSON or CSV file format.

Figure 5: Results of the calculation and the possibility to save the results a JSON file

4. Technical Background

The web application was designed as a modular application. This means that parts of the app are reusable, exchangeable and upgradable. Therefore, the app was separated in two elements. The user interface was developed with the JavaScript framework Angular to provide a state-of-the-art user experience. The underlying module contains the calculation algorithm and was created with WebAssembly. This allows for reuse of the model in other applications and creates a sustainable implementation for further developments.

5. Dissemination

In order to disseminate the web application to a wider audience the implementation will be presented during a FoodChain-Lab workshop in the fall of 2021. Here it is planned to explain the ideas and underlying assumptions this model is based on and provide an example on how a workflow during a foodborne outbreak investigation using this app could look like, how the interaction between the implementation of the model and other methods works and how to interpret the results of the model. After a short demonstration of the app we want to provide a data set of a simulated outbreak to the participants. The attendees will then be requested to use this data and execute the model on their own. During this session we will facilitate the learning activities of the participants, answer questions and provide help if needed. A final Q&A session is planned to answer remaining questions.